

USING DYNAMIC CAPABILITIES TO DRIVE THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE FIRM: THE MODERATING ROLE OF INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENTAL DYNAMISM

Nithya Piumi Parameswara (Ph.D. Student)

Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) | School of Management

Yuosre F. Badir (Supervisor)

Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) | School of Management

Björn Frank (Co-Supervisor)

Faculty of Commerce, Waseda University, Tokyo, Japan

ABSTRACT

The digital transformation (DT) is a complex, revolutionary, and continuous process of strategic renewal. It requires firms to invest resources, but these firms often fail in pursuing the DT. Drawing on the dynamic capability perspective, the complementary assets view, and the contingency theory, this study examines the effect of firms' dynamic capabilities (sensing and seizing capabilities) on their DT, and the moderating role of internal and external environmental dynamism. The analysis of lagged multi-source data collected from 122 firms (244 respondents) revealed that the sensing and seizing capabilities, individually and in combination, positively influence the degree of DT. The dynamism of the firm's external environment negatively moderates the influence of these capabilities. With regards to the firm's internal environment, leadership dynamism and organizational dynamism both have a U-shaped moderating effect on the influence of the sensing capability, and leadership dynamism has an inverse U-shaped moderating effect on the influence of the seizing capability.

Keywords: digital transformation; dynamic capability; external environment; internal environment.

PURPOSE/PROBLEM

The fourth industrial revolution has become a catalyst for either digitally transforming or disrupting firms in several industries (Kane, 2019). The digital transformation (DT) of firms involves simultaneous major changes in key activity domains (e.g., operations, marketing, and/or business modeling) (Wischnevsky & Damanpour, 2006). It can be described as a complex, revolutionary, and continuous process (Liu et al., 2011) of strategic renewal (Warner & Wäger, 2019), which demands updates and fundamental changes of the resources of such firms. To survive any disruption and remain competitive, firms are rushing to adopt digital technologies (McGrath & McManus, 2020). The DT has become a strategic imperative on the agenda of business leaders (Fitzgerald et al., 2014; Hess et al., 2016; Singh and Hess, 2017), who dedicate and redirect their firms' valuable resources and capabilities to the DT (Vial, 2019; Warner & Wäger, 2019). However, despite the leadership's awareness of the potential disruption and investment required to adopt digital technologies, research shows that there are performance differentials between the DT levels of firms (Kane, 2019) and that many firms fail to fully achieve the DT (AlNuaimi et al., 2022; Bresciani et al., 2021). Therefore, the relationship between a firm's resources and its DT performance (i.e., the degree of its DT) needs further investigation.

To examine the relationship between a firm's resources and its performance, and to explain the performance differentials among firms in a context characterized by volatility and dynamism in the firm's internal and external environments, strategy scholars rely on the dynamic capability (DC) perspective, which explains an organization's ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure its resources to respond to rapidly changing environments (Teece et al., 1997; Zahra et al., 2006). Following suit, technology management research has, conceptually (Vial, 2019) and qualitatively (i.e., case study research) (Ghosh et al., 2022; Matarazzo et al., 2021; Warner & Wäger, 2019), suggested a relationship between a firm's DCs and DT. However, while DCs consists of broad components, such as sensing opportunities (and threats) and seizing opportunities, the extant literature has not explored the extent to which different DC affect the DT. Theoretically and empirically, it is thus still unclear how a firm's individual DCs can influence its DT. Moreover, building on the complementary asset perspective of a firm, which suggests that there is a strong relationship of complementarity among a firm's individual capabilities and that some interaction between two or more capabilities may provide more value than either could individually (Foss, 1998; Galbreath, 2016), it is unclear whether a firm's sensing and seizing capabilities interact and complement each other in influencing the degree of DT. Therefore, this article examines the individual and interactive influence of a firm's DCs on its degree of DT.

Furthermore, prior research suggests that a firm's performance may depend on its internal and external environments (Mckee et al., 1989) and on whether these environments are perceived as either stable or dynamic (Perez-Luno et al., 2014). In this regard, the contingency perspective has been proposed as a theoretical lens to examine the alignment of a firm with its business environment, and the effect of this alignment on its performance. Following this line of research, several scholars examine the effect of a firm's internal and external environments on the relationship between DCs and performance (Schilke, 2014; Wilden et al., 2013). However, the moderating effect of a firm's internal and external environmental dynamism on the effect of DCs on the DT has not been examined, which is surprising given that Industry 4.0 in general, and firms' DT effort in particular, may cause disruption and create a dynamic environment that challenges such firms' performance level (Zhu et al., 2021).

In order to address these gaps in the literature, we draw on the DC, complementary assets, and contingency perspectives to answer the following three research questions: 1. What is the effect of DCs on the degree of DT? 2. Do a firm's different DCs complement each other in creating an effect on the degree of DT? 3. What is the role of the internal and external environmental dynamism in moderating the relationship between a firm's DCs and its degree of DT? We develop a conceptual model (see Figure 1) that links a firm's DCs, individually and in combination, to its level of DT and accounts for the contingency aspect of the firm's internal and external environments.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework and hypotheses

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

We designed two separate surveys for managers. The first survey, aimed at middle managers, measured the independent and moderating variables of the sensing capability, seizing capability, leadership dynamism, and organizational dynamism. The second survey, aimed at the senior managers of the same firms, measured the moderating variable of environmental dynamism and the dependent variable of degree of DT. In addition, we collected objective information about the sample firms.

The sample was drawn from the population of electrical and electronic manufacturing organizations in Thailand that have implemented Industry 4.0 technologies within their organization. This population selection was made for two reasons. First, being high-tech industries, they typically concentrate on technologies that can scale and change the company and its operations, resulting in a flood of new goods and services. This creates a natural tendency to enforce the required changes in the organization effortlessly. Hence, the selection of high technology industries allows the study to evade the possible confounding variable of organizational inertia, that is, the inability to implement structural improvements in the face of significant external changes which could hinder DT (Gilbert, 2005). Second, the electronics industry is one of the five industries targeted for the implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies under the Thailand 4.0 initiative. Hence, the use of Industry 4.0 technologies could be expected in a considerable number of organizations.

FINDINGS

The descriptive statistics indicate that the average firm in our sample has partially adopted digital technologies and has developed DCs to a certain extent. Our sample includes a broad range of medium-sized to larger firms. The average respondent has worked for 22 years and for about 12 years in the current firm. Among our respondents, 50% of the middle managers and 31% of the senior managers are female.

Our hypothesis tests show that the sensing capability has a marginally significant (two-sided $p < .1$, corresponding to one-sided $p < .05$ for the one-sided H1a) positive effect on the degree of DT in Model 2 (without the moderating effects), but not in Model 3, where the effects are moderated by the internal and external business environment of the firms. H1a is thus marginally supported in Model 2, but not in Model 3. Hence, the sensing capability has only a weaker effect on average, but a stronger effect under certain environmental conditions. Furthermore, in Model 3 the seizing capability has a positive effect on the degree of DT (H1b is supported). This effect is moderated positively by the sensing capability (H2 is supported). Thus, it is stronger when a firm has a higher sensing capability.

Moreover, the interaction effects of the squared terms of the moderating variables indicate that leadership dynamism has a U-shaped moderating effect on the positive effect of the sensing capability on DT (H3a is supported). Sensing capability does not have any effect at a medium level of leadership dynamism, whereas it has a strong effect at both lower and higher levels of leadership dynamism. In addition, leadership dynamism has an inverted U-shaped moderating effect on the positive effect of the seizing capability on DT (H3b is supported). The results shows that the effect of the seizing capability is very strong at a slightly below-average level of leadership dynamism. This effect becomes much weaker at both lower and higher levels of leadership dynamism. It may even turn negative with an extremely high level of leadership dynamism. Organizational dynamism has a U-shaped moderating effect on the effect of the sensing capability on DT (H4 is supported). The effect of the sensing capability is strongly positive at a lower level of organizational dynamism, zero at a medium level of organizational dynamism, and slightly negative (almost zero) at a higher level of organizational dynamism. From there, it increases again for very high levels of organizational dynamism. Moreover, environmental dynamism negatively moderates the positive effect of the sensing capability and seizing capability (H5a/b is supported).

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

Consistent with most conceptual and qualitative research, our empirical study establishes a positive effect of the sensing and seizing capabilities on the degree of DT (Ghosh et al., 2022; Matarazzo et al., 2021; Warner & Wäger, 2019). Furthermore, we find that the combination of these two capabilities creates a positive effect on the degree of DT. This sheds light on the fact that the ability to sense opportunities within the business environment is not a solitary capability. Instead, it plays a vital role in shaping how a firm's seizing capability leads to DT. This shows that both capabilities together create a synergistic effect.

In contrast to the extant DC research, which examines linear moderating effects of characteristics related to the internal environment of the firm (Wilden et al., 2013), this study observes a U-shaped and inverse U-shaped moderating effect of leadership dynamism on the effects of sensing and seizing capabilities, respectively. In the case of the sensing capability, extremely high and low levels of leadership dynamism promote better utilization of the sensing capability for DT, while intermediate levels of leadership dynamism hinder the process. Contrastingly, extremely high and low levels of leadership dynamism hinder utilization of the seizing capability of DT, while intermediate levels of leadership dynamism promote the process. Furthermore, the moderating effect of organizational dynamism demonstrates a U-shaped relationship, which shows that lower levels of organizational dynamism support the effect of the sensing capability on the degree of DT.

Regarding the moderating effect of external environmental dynamism, the literature highlights three different positions about the role of DCs. The first one indicates that the effect of DCs on competitive advantage is comparatively small at lower levels of external environmental dynamism (Winter, 2003; Zahra et al., 2006; Zollo & Winter, 2002), and the second one questions the use of DCs in highly dynamic external business environments (Amit & Zott, 2015; Danneels, 2008; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Jansen et al., 2006). A third stream of research shows an inverse U-shaped moderating effect of external environmental dynamism on the effect of DCs on competitive advantage (Schilke, 2014). Our study finds a negative moderating effect of external environmental dynamism on the effect of DCs. This shows that high levels of external environmental dynamism weaken the relationship between DCs and DT. While our results are thus more in line with the second position in the literature, we still contend that DCs are important and vital in a dynamic external environment, but they are less effective due to the disruptive and uncertain nature of external environmental dynamism.

Theoretical contribution. The present study provides an important contribution to the emerging literature on the DT. First, our study combines the concept of DCs with the DT and quantitatively confirms that DCs positively affect the degree of DT. Thus, our empirical study confirms the proposition presented in other theoretical and qualitative studies (Ghosh et al., 2022; Matarazzo et al., 2021; Warner & Wäger, 2019). Second, our study examines and verifies the complementary effect of DCs on the DT, which has not been tested previously. Surprisingly, there are minimal studies regarding the complementary effect of DCs, and none in the context of DT. Hence, our study fills this gap in the DC literature and also in the DT literature. Third, our study clarifies the effect of two key contingencies, which are the dynamism of the internal and external business environment, in altering the strength of the DC-DT relationship. Although internal and external contingency factors have been studied in the context of firm performance, there are minimal studies that focus on the context of DT. This study addresses this gap and thus contributes to the literature on DT.

Managerial implications. Our results indicate that the development of DCs is strategically desirable for managers because DCs help restructure a firm to enable it to sense and seize new opportunities and avoid threats. We show that managers can develop and utilize these capabilities in ways that support the DT of the firm. The results stress the importance of both sensing and seizing capabilities as drivers of the DT. That is, systematically developing an enhanced ability to scan the environment for opportunities and threats and an ability to quickly exploit opportunities when they arise can enable the firm to keep up with a changing environment. DCs enable the firm to adopt these digital technologies more quickly and in more meaningful ways. Moreover, we show that developing a superior sensing capability also helps maximize the benefits to be achieved from a superior seizing capability. These two types of DCs support each other.

Furthermore, we show that DCs are not equally effective across different internal and external environments of the firm. Both capabilities are less effective when the external technological and market environment of the firm is more dynamic (i.e., exhibits more changes). However, we still contend that they are important for managers to develop despite a lower effectiveness. Regarding the firm's internal environment, we advise firms to invest in developing a superior sensing capability especially when the firm has a very high or very low level of leadership dynamism (i.e., the degree of decentralized, informal, and flexible procedures) and organizational dynamism (i.e., the degree of integration of internal resources). By contrast, we recommend that firms invest in developing a superior seizing capability when the firm has an intermediate level of leadership dynamism. Under these limited conditions, the respective capabilities are more effective in stimulating and helping implement organizational change, as necessary for the DT.

Firms could enhance its sensing and seizing capabilities by building relationships with customer, suppliers, and competitors can help firms stay abreast of market trends, emerging technologies, and potential disruptions. Firms with strong external networks are more likely to be aware of new market opportunities and threats (Zajac and Olsen, 1993) and have better opportunities in seizing required resources. Further, encouraging employees to think outside the box and experimenting with new ideas can help firms identify new opportunities and stay ahead of the competition. According to Christensen and Bower (1996), a culture of innovation is critical to sensing and responding to disruptive changes in the market.

Limitations and directions for future research. The study is constrained by two limitations, which also represent a fruitful base for future research. First, we focus on the sensing and seizing capabilities, while we have not studied the effect of the firm's transforming capabilities and their complementary effects. We encourage future research on this topic. Second, we collected the data from firms in the electrical and electronics industry in Thailand. While this is an appropriate context for testing our hypotheses, it remains unclear to which degree the results can be generalized to other contexts. Future studies may test our hypotheses in other contexts, such as for different industries, countries, and periods. Such a broader focus may also achieve higher levels of variance in the internal and external factors.

Conclusion. Our findings suggest that DCs drive the DT, individually and in combination, but their effects are contingent on the dynamism of the internal and external environment of the firm. The influence of DCs is thus more complex than has been shown previously. Our study offers new insights into the emerging research area of DT, and we hope it encourages further research.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AlNuaimi, B. K., Kumar Singh, S., Ren, S., Budhwar, P., & Vorobyev, D. (2022). Mastering digital transformation: The nexus between leadership, agility, and digital strategy. *Journal of Business Research*, *145*, 636–648.
- Amit, R., & Zott, C. (2015). Crafting business architecture: The antecedents of business model design. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, *9*(4), 331–350.
- Bresciani, S., Ciampi, F., Meli, F., & Ferraris, A. (2021). Using big data for co-innovation processes: Mapping the field of data-driven innovation, proposing theoretical developments and providing a research agenda. *International Journal of Information Management*, *60*, Article 102347.
- Christensen, C. M., & Bower, J. L. (1996). Customer power, strategic investment, and the failure of leading firms. *Strategic management journal*, *17*(3), 197–218.
- Danneels, E. (2008). Organizational antecedents of second-order competences. *Strategic Management Journal*, *29*(5), 519–543.
- Eisenhardt, K. M., & Martin, J. A. (2000). Dynamic capabilities: What are they? *Strategic Management Journal*, *21*(10), 1105–1121.
- Fitzgerald, M., Kruschwitz, N., Bonnet, D., & Welch, M. (2013). Embracing digital technology: A new strategic imperative. *2013 Digital Transformation Report*. MIT Sloan Management Review and Capgemini Consulting, 1–13.
- Foss, N. J. (1998). The resource-based perspective: An assessment and diagnosis of problems. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, *14*(3), 133–149.
- Galbreath, J. (2016). When do board and management resources complement each other? A study of effects on corporate social responsibility. *Journal of Business Ethics*, *136*, 281–292.
- Ghosh, S., Hughes, M., Hodgkinson, I., & Hughes, P. (2022). Digital transformation of industrial businesses: A dynamic capability approach. *Technovation*, *113*, Article 102414.
- Gilbert, C. G. (2005). Unbundling the structure of inertia: Resource versus routine rigidity. *Academy of Management Journal*, *48*(5), 741–763.
- Hess, T., Benlian, A., Matt, C., & Wiesböck, F. (2016). Options for formulating a digital transformation strategy. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, *15*(2), 123–139.
- Jansen, J. J. P., Bosch, F. A. J. Van Den, & Volberda, H. W. (2006). Exploratory innovation, exploitative innovation, and performance: Effects of organizational antecedents and environmental moderators. *Management Science*, *52*(11), 1661–1674.
- Kane, G. (2019). The technology fallacy: People are the real key to digital transformation. *Research Technology Management*, *62*(6), 44–49.
- Liu, D. Y., Chen, S. W., & Chou, T. C. (2011). Resource fit in digital transformation: Lessons learned from the CBC Bank global e-banking project. *Management Decision*, *49*(10), 1728–1742.
- Matarazzo, M., Penco, L., Profumo, G., & Quaglia, R. (2021). Digital transformation and customer value creation in Made in Italy SMEs: A dynamic capabilities perspective. *Journal of Business Research*, *123*, 642–656.
- McGrath, R., & McManus, R. (2020). Discovery-driven. *Harvard Business Review*, *98*(3), 124–133.

- Mckee, D. O., Varadarajan, P. R., & Pride, W. M. (1989). Strategic adaptability and firm performance: A market-contingent perspective. *Journal of Marketing*, 53(3), 21–35.
- Perez-Luno, A., Gopalakrishnan, S., & Cabrera, R. V. (2014). Innovation and performance: The role of environmental dynamism on the success of innovation choices. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 61(3), 499–510.
- Schilke, O. (2014). On the contingent value of dynamic capabilities for competitive advantage: The nonlinear moderating effect of environmental dynamism. *Strategic Management Journal*, 35(2), 179–203.
- Singh, A., & Hess, T. (2017). How chief digital officers promote the digital transformation of their companies. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 16(1), Article 5.
- Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509–533.
- Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118–144.
- Warner, K. S. R., & Wäger, M. (2019). Building dynamic capabilities for digital transformation: An ongoing process of strategic renewal. *Long Range Planning*, 52(3), 326–349.
- Wilden, R., Gudergan, S. P., & Nielsen, B. B. (2013). Dynamic capabilities and performance: Strategy, structure and environment. *Long Range Planning*, 46(1–2), 72–96.
- Winter, S. G. (2003). Understanding dynamic capabilities. *Strategic Management Journal*, 24(10), 991–995.
- Wischnevsky, J., & Damanpour, F. (2006). Organizational transformation and performance: An examination of three perspectives. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 18(1), 104–128.
- Zahra, S. A., Sapienza, H. J., & Davidsson, P. (2006). Entrepreneurship and dynamic capabilities: A review, model and research agenda. *Journal of Management Studies*, 43(4), 917–955.
- Zajac, E. J., & Olsen, C. P. (1993). From transaction cost to transactional value analysis: Implications for the study of interorganizational strategies. *Journal of management studies*, 30(1), 131–145.
- Zhu, X., Ge, S., & Wang, N. (2021). Digital transformation: A systematic literature review. *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, 162, Article 107774.
- Zollo, M., & Winter, S. G. (2002). Deliberate learning and the evolution of dynamic capabilities. *Organization Science*, 13(3), 339–351.